

Spectrophotometric determination of cadmium(II) using novel oxime-hydrazones in biological materials

K. B. Chandrasekhar^a and K. Hussain Reddy^{b*}

^aDepartment of Chemistry, JNTU College of Engineering, Anantapur-515 001, India

^bDepartment of Chemistry, Sri Krishnadevaraya University, Anantapur-515 003, India

Fax : 91-08554-29043

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The analytical characteristics of three new oxime-hydrazones are described. The reagents diacetylmonoxime benzoylhydrazone (DMBH), diacetylmonoxime isonicotinoylhydrazone (DMIH) and benzil- α -monoxime isonicotinoylhydrazone (BMIH) give yellow coloured solutions with cadmium(II) in borate buffers. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity of Cd^{II}-DMBH, Cd^{II}-DMIH and Cd^{II}-BMIH are 1.6×10^4 , 2.0×10^4 and 2.5×10^4 dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹ at 348, 346 and 362 nm, and 0.00712, 0.00562 and 0.00450 μ g cm⁻², respectively. BMIH has been used for the spectrophotometric determination of cadmium(II) in some biological samples.

Oxime-hydrazones may be considered as novel reagents because they contain mixed functional groups (two-in-one), viz. oxime and hydrazones. The survey of literature¹ reveals that oxime-hydrazones are not used for the spectrophotometric determination of cadmium(II). We report herein the synthesis and analytical properties of oxime-hydrazones, viz. diacetylmonoxime benzoylhydrazone (DMBH), diacetylmonoxime isonicotinoylhydrazone (DMIH) and benzil- α -monoxime isonicotinoylhydrazone (BMIH). The determination of cadmium(II) using BMIH in different samples has been performed. Analytical characteristics of Cd-DMBH, Cd-DMIH and Cd-BMIH complexes are compared.

Results and Discussion

The reagents DMBH, DMIH and BMIH were prepared by condensing monoxime (diacetylmonoxime, benzil- α -monoxime) with appropriate hydrazide (benzhydrazide or isonicotinic acid hydrazide) in methanol.

R = CH₃, X = CH; DMBH (I)

R = CH₃, X = N; DMIH (II)

R = C₆H₅, X = N; BMIH (III)

The values of the deprotonation of the DMBH, DMIH and BMIH were found to be 3, 5, 2.5 (pK₁) and 7, 9, 9.5

(pK₂), respectively. The pK₁ may be assigned to the deprotonation of imine (NH) through enolization while pK₂ is assigned to deprotonation of oxime hydrogen (=N-OH).

Reaction with metal ions : The samples were prepared by mixing buffer, metal ion and reagent solutions and its absorbance measured at 250–600 nm against the reagent blank.

The reaction of some important metal ions were tested at different pH values. The results are summarized in Table 1. The cadmium complexes of DMBH, DMIH and BMIH showed absorption maxima at 348, 346 and 364 nm, respectively. Hence analytical studies were made at these wavelengths. The complexes showed maximum and constant absorbance in the pH range 9.0–9.5, 8.7–9.3 and 8.3–8.8, respectively. Hence further studies were carried out at pH 9.3, 9.0 and 8.5 for the determination of cadmium using DMBH, DMIH and BMIH, respectively.

A 10-fold molar excess of the reagent (DMBH, DMIH or BMIH) was found sufficient for full colour development. The colour reactions between Cd^{II} and DMBH, DMIH and BMIH was instantaneous at room temperature. The absorbance of the complex was found to be constant for more than 2 h with DMBH and DMIH and 1 h using BMIH. Problems due to the hydrolysis of Cd^{II} were not encountered, which is evident from reproducibility of absorbance value (Table 2). The order of addition of buffer, cadmium(II) and reagents had no adverse effect on the absorbance.

Beer's law is obeyed in the concentration range 0.22–4.95, 0.22–5.40 and 0.45–4.50 μ g ml⁻¹ of Cd^{II} using DMBH and DMIH and BMIH, respectively. The molar ab-

Table 1. Analytical characteristics of DMBH, DMIH and BIMI compounds

Metal ion	Using DMBH				Using DMIH				Using BIMI			
	pH	λ_{\max} nm	Colour of complex	$10^4 \epsilon$ $\text{dm}^{-3} \text{mol}^{-1}$ cm^{-1}	pH	λ_{\max} nm	Colour of complex	$10^4 \epsilon$ $\text{dm}^{-3} \text{mol}^{-1}$ cm^{-1}	pH	λ_{\max} nm	Colour of complex	$10^4 \epsilon$ $\text{dm}^{-3} \text{mol}^{-1}$ cm^{-1}
Pb ^{II}	10.0–11.0	372	Yellow	1.25	10.0–11.0	374	Yellow	1.25	10.0–11.0	405	Yellow	1.00
Cd ^{II}	9.0–9.5	348	Yellow	1.60	8.75–9.25	346	Yellow	2.00	8.25–8.75	364	Light yellow	2.50
Ni ^{II}	8.0–10.0	362	Yellow	2.12	8.0–8.5	366	Yellow	1.75	8.0–9.0	398	Greenish yellow	1.45
Cu ^{II}	8.0–10.0	346	Greenish yellow	1.36	8.0–9.0	346	Greenish yellow	1.12	8.0–9.0	346	Greenish yellow	1.19
Co ^{II}	5.0–9.0	340	Orange red	1.10	5.0–9.0	348	Orange red	1.40	5.0–9.0	350–380	Orange red	1.50
Fe ^{II}	5.0–9.0	360	Red	1.60	–	–	–	–	5.0–9.0	380–400	Red	–

sorptivity of Cd-DMBH, Cd-DMIH and Cd-BMIH complexes are 1.6×10^4 , 2.0×10^4 and $2.5 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$, respectively. The important physicochemical and analytical characteristics of the complexes are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2. Physicochemical characteristics of cadmium(II) complexes

Characteristics	Cd ^{II} -DMBH	Cd ^{II} -DMIH	Cd ^{II} -BIMI
λ_{\max} (nm)	348	346	364
Mole of reagent required per mole of Cd ^{II}	10	8	10
Optimum pH range	9.0–9.5	8.7–9.3	8.3–8.8
Beer's law validity range ($\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$)	0.2–4.95	0.22–5.40	0.45–4.50
Regression coefficient	0.995	0.998	0.996
Optimum concentration range ($\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$)	0.45–4.50	0.90–4.95	0.90–4.00
Molar absorptivity ($\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$)	1.6×10^4	2.0×10^4	2.5×10^4
Sandell's sensitivity ($\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$)	0.00711	0.00562	0.0045
Composition of the complex ^a	1 : 1	1 : 2	1 : 1
Stability constant of the complex ^b	3.8×10^5	2.9×10^9	1.2×10^5
Standard deviation ^c	0.002	0.005	0.006
Relative standard deviation, %	0.6	1.3	1.2

^aDetermined by Job's and mole ratio methods.

^bDetermined by Job's method.

^cFor ten replicate determinations (in the determination of $2.25 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of Cd^{II}).

Interferences : The effect of various diverse ions on the determination of Cd^{II} was studied to find out the tolerance limits of foreign ions in the present methods. The tolerance limit of a foreign ion was taken as the amount of foreign ion required to cause an error of $\pm 2\%$ in the absorbance. The

tolerance limit ($\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) values of diverse ions in the determination of $2.25 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ cadmium using BIMI, DMIH and DMBH, respectively, are triethanolamine (960, 920, 950), tartrate (656, 656, 656), citrate (582, 836, 500), iodide (507, 508, 406), hypo (314, 449, 370), sulphate (307, 384, 320), thiourea (304, 245, 243), oxalate (274, 392, 255), bromide (256, 240, 320), nitrate (248, 223, 243), thiocyanate (232, 232, 232), phosphate (190, 135, 8), urea (168, 228, 216), chloride (192, 114, 113), fluoride (80, 76, 46), W^{VI} (74, 2, 21), Bi^{III} (17, 3, 4), Mo^{VI} (16, 12, 13), Ag^I (9, 2, 3), Al^{III} (6, 7, 6), V^V (2, 1, 1) can be tolerated, but interference from Cu^{II} (4) is masked with thiourea (1975) and Fe^{III} (3) with NaF (150). A $1 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of Hg^{II}, Mn^{II} and Zn^{II} did not interfere in all the methods. The data suggest that BIMI reagent is more selective when compared with other reagents.

Applications : Cadmium(II) was determined in different biological samples, viz. raddish flesh, cabbage and cigarette tobacco. The results are presented in Table 3.

Conclusion : The present method using DMBH, DMIH and BIMI compares favourably with recently reported spectrophotometric methods^{2,3} for the determination of cadmium(II). The method using BIMI is found to be more sensitive and selective for the spectrophotometric determination of cadmium in aqueous medium as to DMBH and BIMI. The reagents are easy to synthesize. The present methods are simple and rapid without the need for heating or extraction.

Experimental

Preparation of DMBH and DMIH : The reagents were prepared by refluxing a mixture of diacetylmonoxime (1 mmol) and benzhydrazide or isonicotinic hydrazide (1 mol) in methanol (30 ml) for 4 h. The resulting hydrazone was

Table 3. Analysis of cadmium in biological samples

Sample	Sample		Cadmium found ^a ($\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$)			
	stock solution ml	Sample taken ml	Using BMIH reagent	Average	AAS	Average
Cigarette Tobacco-1 ^b	50	4	19.74		19.98	
		6	20.34	19.96±0.38	20.30	19.97±0.33
		8	19.82		19.65	
Cigarette Tobacco-2 ^b	50	4	21.55		21.55	
		6	22.16	21.75±0.41	23.50	22.06±1.44
		8	21.55		21.14	
Raddish ^c	50	4	1.75		1.81	
		6	1.75	1.81±0.13	1.75	1.84±0.13
		8	1.94		1.97	
Cabbage ^c	50	7	0.146		0.162	
		8	0.152	0.149±0.003	0.153	0.157±0.005

^aMean of three determinations. ^bDried sample ^cWet sample.

washed with cold methanol and dried under reduced pressure : DMBH (60%), m.p. 206–208°; DMIH (75%), 171–173°. Benzil- α -monoxime was prepared by following the literature procedure⁴. BMIH was prepared by refluxing a mixture of benzil- α -monoxime dissolved in hot methanol and isoniazid dissolved in hot water, (50%), m.p. 178°.

IR spectra of DMBH, DMIH and BMIH showed bands at 3325, 3175, 3390; 1768, 1671, 1676; 1648, 1605, 1655; 1017, 1027, 930 cm^{-1} respectively assigned to ν_{OH} (oxime), $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$, $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ and $\nu_{\text{N-O}}$ vibrations. ¹H NMR spectra (DMSO- d_6) showed signals at δ 11.61, 11.61, 11.69; 10.72, 10.95, 12.41 due to imino and oxime protons of DMBH, DMIH and BMIH, respectively. The spectrum of DMBH showed multiplet signals due to phenyl protons with 2 : 1 : 2 ratio centred at 7.85 ppm. Isonicotinic moiety protons showed doublet at δ 7.68, 7.69; 8.73, 8.70 in the spectra of DMIH and BMIH, respectively. Strong signals observed at δ 1.7–2.5 were assigned to methyl protons of diacetyl moiety of DMBH and DMIH. Mass spectrum of DMBH showed molecular ion peak at m/z 219 corresponding to the molecular weight. Other peaks are 202 $[\text{M-OH}]^+$, 161 $[\text{M-CH}_3\text{CNOH}]^+$. DMIH and BMIH did not show molecular ion peaks possibly due to less stability of molecular ions, however, it showed peaks at m/z 77, 105, 120, 178, 193, 221 and 239 corresponding to different fragments of reagents.

The pK_a values were determined by recording the UV-visible spectra of micromolar solution ($\sim 10^{-6}$ M) of reagents at various pH values and by taking the arithmetic mean of the values obtained from the measurement at four different

wavelengths.

Reagent solutions (0.01 M) were prepared in dimethylformamide. Hydrochloric acid (1 M)–sodium acetate (1 M) (pH 0.5–3.5); 0.2 M NaOAc–0.2 M AcOH (pH 4–6), and 2 M NH_4Cl –2 M NH_4OH (pH 8–11) solutions were used in the determination of pK_a values of reagents. The standard Cd^{II} solution (1×10^{-2} M) was prepared using cadmium sulfate (E. Merck, G.R.). Solutions of diverse ions of suitable concentrations were prepared using A.R. grade chemicals.

Procedure : An aliquot of the solution containing 0.23–4.95 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of Cd^{II} , borate buffer solution (10 ml) [pH 9.25 (DMBH), 9.0 (DMIH) and 8.5 (BMIH); 10 ml] and 0.01 M reagent (1 ml) was diluted to 25 ml with distilled water. The absorbance of the solution was measured against the corresponding reagent blank and the Cd content computed.

Samples of raddish, cabbage and tobacco³ were prepared by usual procedures.

A Shimadzu 160 A spectrophotometer equipped with 1.0 cm quartz cells and an Elico LI-120 pH meter were used. IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 983 G spectrophotometer, ¹H NMR spectra (CDCl_3) on a Varian XL-300 MHz spectrometer, mass spectra on a Fauning-Mat 8230 spectrometer and AAS on a ECIL 4127 atomic absorption spectrophotometer (HCL-current, 3.5 μA ; wavelength, 228.8 nm; slit-width, 0.5 mm).

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References

1. P. Jain and R. P. Singh, *Talanta*, 1982, **29**, 77; K. I. West and R. T. Pflaum, *Talanta*, 1986, **33**, 807; K. B. Chandrasekhar, Ph.D. Thesis, Sri Krishnadevaraya University, 1999.
2. U. Atsuya, N. Hiroshi, K. Testu and N. Thoru, *Orient. J. Chem.*, 1993, **9**, 268; S. Chakravarty, M. Deb and M. R. Kumar, *J. AOAC Inst.*, 1993, **76**, 604; A. Kumar, A. Solkar and A. Pondey-pratibhar, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1993, **32**, 644; A. Kumar and A. Nigam, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1998, **37**, 845; B. Raman and V. M. Shinde, *Analyst*, 1990, **115**, 93.
3. K. Grudpan and C. G. Taylor, *Talanta*, 1989, **36**, 1005.
4. "Vogel's Text book of Practical Organic Chemistry", eds. B. S. Furniss, A. J. Hannaford, V. Rogers, P. W. G. Smith and A. R. Tatchev, ELBS, London, 1984.